

EUROPEAN
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COVER PAGE AND DECLARATION

	Master of Science (MS) in IT & Data Science
Specialisation:	
Module Code & Module Title:	MSITDS620 Programming languages and software development
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Word Count:	2731
Date of Submission:	22 August 2024

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Table of Content

Introduction-----	1
Main Body -----	2
1. Functionality -----	2
2. Code quality-----	8
3. Database design and implementation -----	10
4. User authentication and authorization -----	13
Conclusion -----	30
References -----	31

Introduction

According to (*UNStOP - Competitions, Quizzes, Hackathons, Scholarships and Internships for Students and Corporates*, n.d.), “In general, the word language refers to the mode of communication used amongst a group of individuals or entities to exchange ideas, give commands, etc. Similarly in the world of programming, the language that software programmers, software engineers, coders, developers, etc. use to communicate with a computer or software is referred to as a programming language. There are thousands of programming languages in use today with many new and upcoming features. So let's move on to discussing the various types of programming languages and discuss some prominent features. With dozens of programming languages available out there, a lot of you might be confused as to which programming language to learn first. Well, to help you navigate this world of confusion, here is a list of the most popular languages that you must know: Python, C++, Kotlin, Perl, JavaScript, Ruby, Rust, R, Java, Swift, MATLAB, Dart, C#, C, Objective-C, Lua, PHP, TypeScript, Scala, Shell Scripting.” From javapoint.com (*Programming Language / What Is Programming Language - Javatpoint*, n.d.) also stated “Several software packages are made using programming languages, together with: Operating structures, Web browsers, Mobile apps, Desktop packages, Video games, General Software program, Business-related software programs, Embedded structures.”

Objective of this report is working on developing a web application using HTML, CSS, JavaScript, and a server-side language. The web application should have several pages and connect a database for storing user data, and implement user authentication and authorization. For this case, a web application of a Company namely, PTC WORKSHOPS locates at Kampot province, Cambodia has been introduced and demonstrated follow along to the criteria. The main features of current web application of this company provide data management such as vehicle repair services and vehicle spare part sales and basic statistical analysis only include total of business income and expense and total of salary each month. This web application is used for loss and profit management and staff management of the company and it was developed by using HTML, CSS, Bootstrap, JavaScript, jQuery for front-end and PHP for a server-side language connect to MySQL database. The database stores two main parts, first part are inventory and sale management, second are staff, attendance and payroll management.

Main Body

1. Functionality

1.1. The web application meets the requirements specified in the assessment task

This web application has been developed by using the combination of several scripting and languages such as HTML, CSS, JavaScript, jQuery, Bootstrap and PHP language connects to MySQL database. And it has been developed follow the requirements by analyze the business flow and collect user requirements to develop this web application with many important functionalities such as protect unauthorized access, encrypt sensitive data, responsive layout and error handling and validation.

1.2. The web application functions correctly and efficiently

The functionalities of the web application are correctly and efficiently by following to software development lifecycle (*What Is the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) and How Does It Work?* / Synopsys, n.d.). It has been planned and analyzed by discussing with the owner of the company to understand the user requirements. Figure 1 and 2 below are the draft of user requirements from the owner of the company that need to be developed to the web application

Summary

Income(I)	Salary Expense(S)	Utility Expense(U)	Profit = I - (S+U)	Spas part (SP)	Net Income (NI) = I - SP

Spas part = Total Invoice - Labor Cost

Service Profit = Service (Invoice) - Salary - Utility.

Figure 1. Draft of summary income and expense that client want to have on the web application

Figure 2. Draft of authorization that client to use on the web application

The database of the web application is encrypted to protect against unauthorized access. Especially in 'table_admin', the 'admin_password' column is encrypted without storing the password in plain text.

Figure 3. MySQL database of the web application

The graphical user interface of the web application is user-friendly by displaying in responsive mode and for the left sidebar menu, it shows all main and sub menu.

Figure 4. Dashboard web page of the web application

The database is reliable by being backed up regularly by administrator and stored in the secured locations.

Figure 5. Backing up MySQL database on PHP MyAdmin

1.3. The responsive design webpages on desktop and mobile devices

Based on (*W3Schools.com*, n.d.) “Bootstrap is a free front-end framework for faster and easier web development. Bootstrap includes HTML and CSS based design templates for typography, forms, buttons, tables, navigation, modals, image carousels and many other, as well as optional JavaScript plugins Bootstrap also gives you the ability to easily create responsive designs.”

Bootstrap is one the most powerful responsive front-end framework that allow web developers use to design website or web application supports multiple devices in responsive mode. In ‘<row>’ class and ‘<div>’ classes of Bootstrap, it can make the web pages display in different mode such as desktop, laptop, tablet, or smart phone. The figure below displays web application layout in desktop and laptop mode by divided to three columns including left menu in first column and dashboard panels in second and third columns merged together.

Figure 6. Full layout of the web application displays on the desktop or laptop screen.

On the other hand, when the smart phone or tablet device access the web application, the layout changes to one column by displaying left menu to the top and dashboard panels to the bottom.

Figure 7. Layout of the web application displays on the tablet or smart phone screen.

1.4. The web application has appropriate error handling and validation

In 'add_staff.php' page, there are many error handling and validation tasks. All red star fields are required for users to input data. For 'salary' and 'order' text fields are required to input in number only. For 'staff type' text field is required users to select an item of all items.

Add Staff

Staff Card Number: ST-0100

Staff Full Name *: Mony Ho

Salary *: 500

Staff Type *: Senior Mechanician

Date of Birth *: 1987-12-10

Start Working *: 2024-08-06

Place of Birth *: Kampot

Address *: Kampot

Phnone Number *: 012603314

Order *: 100

All (*) fields are required.

Save

Figure 8. Data validation implementation on 'add_staff.php' page

For 'start working' and 'place of birth' text fields are use 'bootstrap-datepicker' library to allow users pick a date time without inputting it manually (*Bootstrap-datepicker — Bootstrap-datepicker Documentation, n.d.*).

Start Working *: 2024-08-06

Place of Birth *:

Address *:

Phnone Number *:

Order *:

All (*) fields are required.

Save

Figure 9. Data validation with date time picker library

2. Code quality

2.1. The code is well-organized, readable, and maintainable

To write and manage well-organized, readable and maintainable code there are some main points to consider including meaningful names of variables or functions like using camelCase and consist code style including indentation or line breaks. Figure 11 display the code in 'login.php' that declare variables in 'camelCase' and assign database name, table name, column name in 'sneak_case'.

2.2. The code follows best practices and coding standards

Gitlab is one the best platforms that provides many features for administrator to work with version control software (*The Most-comprehensive AI-powered DevSecOps Platform*, n.d.). The web application uses Gitlab to synchronize project code and also the best place to back up the project source code. It is very handfull when development in team. So the developers can works separately in different branches and version until the project is competed than the project manager can merges them together into one main branch.

Figure 10. Gitlab vision control system platform on web

2.3. The code is well-documented with comments and/or inline documentation

There are two types of comments in PHP server-side language such as inline comment and multi-line comments. Comments are very important in the project code, it reminds developers

what does the block of code mean without re-test the code again. In figure 11 is the code in 'login.php' page that uses inline comments to explain the meaning of some line of codes.

2.4. The code is free of syntax and logical errors

```
login.php
1  <?php
2  session_start();
3  $msg = "";
4  //Include database information from connection.php
5  include("connection.php");
6  //Start Button Click
7  if(isset($_POST["buttonLogin"])){
8      try{
9          //Get admin name and password from text fields in form
10         $adminName = ltrim(rtrim($_POST["adminName"]));
11         $adminPassword = md5(ltrim(rtrim($_POST["adminPassword"])));
12         //Compare admin name and password with table admin
13         $qry = mysqli_query($con,'select * from table_admin where admin_name="'. $adminName.
14         '' and admin_password="'. $adminPassword. ''') or die(mysqli_error($con));
15         //Can retrieve one record means the cridentail is correct
16         if(mysqli_num_rows($qry) ==1){
17             $_SESSION["adminName"] = $adminName;
18             $qry_session=mysqli_query($con,'select * from table_admin where admin_name="'.
19             $adminName. ''');
20             $row_session=mysqli_fetch_array($qry_session,MYSQLI_ASSOC);
21             //Pass admin id and role to sessions to use in next page
22             $_SESSION["adminId"]=$row_session["adminId"];
23             $_SESSION["role"]=$row_session["role"];
24             //redirect to index.php
25             header("location:index.php");
26         }
27         //Cannot retrieve record means the cridentail is incorrect.
28         else{
29             $msg = '
30             <div class="alert alert-danger">
31             <strong>Failed!</strong> Admin Name or Admin Password is incorrect.
32             </div>
33             ' ;
34         }
35     }
36     catch (Exception $e) {
37         //display error message
38         echo $e->errorMessage();
39     }
40 }
41 //End Button Click
42 ?>
```

Figure 11. Applying comments, indentations and error handing to the 'login.php' web page

In errors have been categorized into many types such as syntax error, logical errors and run time error. For syntax error is discovered while writing the code. It will not allow the page to run until the developers update them from incorrect to correct all first. Logical error is very sensitive for developers to avoid. To clear all logical errors, developers must test several times to recognize that the calculation, logical condition are match to the user requirements. Moreover, there is another error called run time error. It occurs when users input something not match to the code condition. For example, when the user input number value to calculate with string value. This calculation will produce a run time error. To protect the run time errors, exception handling can be used with try catch function. It helps the webpage still running and display the message for the user about the error without closing or making the page is not responding. In figure 11 is the code in 'login.php' page that uses exception handling to protect run time error.

3. Database design and implementation

3.1. The database schema is well-designed and normalized

The database of the web application is designed and normalized very well. For relationship follows the 'one-to-many' relationship by primary tables have the 'id' column with primary key connect the relationship to related tables have related column with foreign keys (Dittofi, 2023). Chris (2022) of freecodecamp wrote that "When a table is in 2NF, it eliminates repeating groups and redundancy, but it does not eliminate transitive partial dependency. This means a non-prime attribute (an attribute that is not part of the candidate's key) is dependent on another non-prime attribute. This is what the third normal form (3NF) eliminates." This case, 'table_invoice' table is applied 3NF with 'staff_id' and 'admin_id' columns. The 'staff_id' column refers to the id of the staff who is responsible to repair vehicles and 'admin_id' refers to the id of admin who enter the data to the web application system.

Figure 12. Database schema of the web application

3.2. The database is implemented correctly and efficiently

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Comments	Extra
1	id	int(11)			No	None		AUTO_INCREMENT
2	staff_id	int(11)			No	None		
3	salary_date	datetime			No	None		
4	amount	float			No	None		
5	bonus	float			No	None		

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Comments	Extra
1	id	int(11)			No	None		AUTO_INCREMENT
2	staff_id	int(11)			No	None		
3	date	date			No	None		
4	attendance	int(11)			No	None		
5	reason	varchar(100)	utf8mb4_general_ci		No	None		

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Comments	Extra
1	staff_id	int(11)			No	None		AUTO_INCREMENT
2	staff_card_number	varchar(100)	utf8mb4_general_ci		Yes	NULL		
3	staff_full_name	varchar(100)	utf8mb4_general_ci		No	None		
4	date_of_birth	date			No	None		
5	start_working_date	date			No	None		
6	sex	varchar(100)	utf8mb4_general_ci		No	None		
7	place_of_birth	varchar(100)	utf8mb4_general_ci		Yes	NULL		
8	address	varchar(100)	utf8mb4_general_ci		Yes	NULL		
9	phone_number	varchar(100)	utf8mb4_general_ci		No	None		
10	staff_photo	varchar(100)	utf8mb4_general_ci		Yes	NULL		
11	salary	float			No	None		
12	type_id	int(11)			No	None		
13	staff_order	int(11)			No	None		
14	admin_id	int(11)			No	None		

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Comments	Extra
1	invoice_id	int(11)			No	None		AUTO_INCREMENT
2	invoice_date	datetime			No	None		
3	customer_name	varchar(100)	utf8mb4_general_ci		No	None		
4	customer_phone	varchar(100)	utf8mb4_general_ci		No	None		
5	plate_number	varchar(100)	utf8mb4_general_ci		No	None		
6	staff_id	int(11)			No	None		
7	sub_total	double			No	None		
8	discount	double			No	None		
9	grand_total	double			No	None		
10	payment	double			No	None		
11	paid	tinyint(4)			No	None		
12	admin_id	int(11)			No	None		

Figure 13. All table in the database – part 1

The database is implemented follow the database schema correctly and efficiently by defining table names, set primary key to the primary columns, and prepare foreign keys in related tables to connect with primary tables. And set appropriate data types for each field to columns in the tables. The tables below are created and connected the relationship follow to the database schema.

Figure 14. All table in the database – part 2

3.3. The database is used appropriately within the web application

The database that has been used with the web application is MySQL Database. The database information that PHP need for connection including hostname is 'localhost', username is 'ptc', password is 'RootAdmin11!!' and database's name is 'PTCDB'. The database information is stored in 'connection.php' page. And PHP used 'mysqli_connect' function to connect to MySQL database.

```

connection.php
1  <?php
2  //Database information
3  $con = mysqli_connect("localhost","ptc","RootAdmin11!!","PTCDB")
4  or die(mysqli_error($con));
5
6  //Function converts number to USD currency
7  function dls($num){
8      return "$ ". number_format($num, 2, '.', '');
9  }
10 ?>

```

Figure 15. PHP code connects to MySQL database

4. User authentication and authorization

4.1. The web application implements user authentication and authorization correctly

In 'table_admin' table stores admin name in 'admin_name' column and password in 'admin_password' column to check user authentication when user's login, they must input their credential. If it is correct, the web application will redirect to dashboard page (index.php). But if it is not correct, users must re-input the correct credential.

Figure 16. 'login.php' web page for authentication.

After redirecting to 'index.php' page, a session namely '\$_SESSION["adminId"]' will check if it is equal 1 (admin), so all the menu items display for admin user to use such as 'List Staffs' and 'Salary' menu link items.

Figure 17. Authorization of admin role by displaying full menu items

On the other hand, if ‘\$_SESSION["adminId"]’ check and if it is equal 2 (staff), so some the menu items display for staff user to use but some are hidden such as ‘List Staffs’ and ‘Salary’ menu link items. So, the authorization in this web application has been separated to two, number 1 is admin and number 2 is staff and these values are stored in ‘role’ column in ‘tabe_admin’ table.

Figure 18. Authorization of staff role by displaying some menu items

4.2. The web application handles user sessions appropriately

Almost all pages except 'login.php' page check the user's information with '\$_SESSION["adminName"]', if there is no value in it, this means there no login process. So the 'index.php' web page redirects back to 'login.php' to force user must login with correct credential first before using other web pages.

```
index.php
1  <?php
2  session_start();
3  if(!isset($_SESSION["adminName"])){
4  |   header("location:login.php");
5  }
```

Figure 19. Using session in 'index.php' web page

The codes below are the full line of code in 'login.php', 'index.php' and 'logout.php'. But these web pages are included from another separated PHP files such as database connection information in 'connection.php', header of web page in 'header.php', and left menu of the web pages in 'left_menu.php'.

Codes in 'login.php' page:

```
<?php

session_start();

$msg = "";

//Include database information from connection.php

include("connection.php");

//Start Button Click
```

```

if(isset($_POST["buttonLogin"])){

    try{

        //Get admin name and password from text fields in form

        $adminName = ltrim(rtrim($_POST["adminName"]));

        $adminPassword = md5(ltrim(rtrim($_POST["adminPassword"])));

        //Compare admin name and password with table admin

        $qry = mysqli_query($con,'select * from table_admin where admin_name="'. $adminName.

        "' and admin_password="'. $adminPassword. "'") or die(mysqli_error($con));

        //Can retrieve one record means the credential is correct

        if(mysqli_num_rows($qry) ==1){

            $_SESSION["adminName"] = $adminName;

            $qry_session=mysqli_query($con,'select * from table_admin where admin_name="'.

            $adminName. "'");

            $row_session=mysqli_fetch_array($qry_session,MYSQLI_ASSOC);

            //Pass admin id and role to sessions to use in next page

            $_SESSION["adminId"]=$row_session["adminId"];

            $_SESSION["role"]=$row_session["role"];

            //redirect to index.php

            header("location:index.php");

        }
    }
}

```

```
//Cannot retrieve record means the credential is incorrect.

else{

    $msg = '

    <div class="alert alert-danger">

    <strong>Failed!</strong> Admin Name or Admin Password is incorrect.

    </div>

    ;

    }

}

catch (Exception $e) {

    //display error message

    echo $e->errorMessage();

}

}

//End Button Click

?>

<!DOCTYPE html>

<html lang="en">

<head>

    <title>Login</title>
```

```
<meta charset="utf-8">

<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">

<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/bootstrap.min.css">

<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/custom.css" />

<script src="js/jquery-3.5.1.js"></script>

<script src="js/bootstrap.bundle.min.js"></script>

</head>

<body>

  <div class="container">

    <div class="row" style="margin-top:20px;">

      <div class="col-md-1">

      </div>

      <div class="col-md-10">

        <div class="card">

          <div class="card-header">

            <h3>Login</h3>

          </div>

          <div class="card-body">

            <?php echo $msg; ?>

            <form action="<?php echo $_SERVER["PHP_SELF"];?>" method="post">
```

```

<div class="form-row">

  <label for="email" class="col-sm-3 col-form-label">Admin Name <span
    class="req">*</span></label>

  <input type="text" class="form-control col-sm-9" placeholder="Enter
Admin Name" name="adminName" required>

</div><br />

<div class="form-row">

  <label for="pwd" class="col-sm-3 col-form-label">Password <span
class="req">*</span></label>

  <input type="password" class="form-control col-sm-9" placeholder="Enter
Admin Password" name="adminPassword" required>

</div><br />

<div class="form-row" style="text-align:center;">

  <label for="pwd" class="col-sm-12 col-form-label"><span class="req">All
(*) fields are required. </span></label>

</div><br />

<button type="submit" class="btn btn-primary btn-block"
name="buttonLogin">Login</button>

</form>

</div>

</div>

```

```
</div>

<div class="col-md-1">

</div>

</div>

</div>

</body>

</html>
```

Codes in 'index.php' page:

```
<?php

session_start();

//Check login session

if(!isset($_SESSION["adminName"])){

    header("location:login.php");

}

//Include database information

include("connection.php");

?>

<!DOCTYPE html>

<html lang="en">
```

```
<head>

<title>Dashboard</title>

<meta charset="utf-8">

<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">

<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/bootstrap.min.css">

<script src="js/jquery-3.5.1.js"></script>

<script src="js/bootstrap.bundle.min.js"></script>

</head>

<body>

<!-- Include codes from header page -->

<?php include("header.php"); ?>

<div class="container-fluid">

<div class="row">

<!-- Include codes from left menu page -->

<?php include("left_menu.php");?>

<div class="col-md-9">

<h1>Dashboard</h1>

<div class="row">

<div class="col-sm-6">

<div class="list-group">
```

```

<a class="list-group-item list-group-item-warning">Invoice Management</a>

<a href="create_invoice.php" class="list-group-item">Create Invoice</a>

<a href="list_invoice.php" class="list-group-item">List Invoices</a>

<a class="list-group-item"> Total Invoices: <span class="badge badge-
warning">

<?php

$qi =mysqli_query($con,"select * from table_invoice");

echo mysqli_num_rows($qi);

?>

</span></a>

</div>

</div>

<div class="col-sm-6">

<div class="list-group">

<div class="list-group">

<a class="list-group-item list-group-item-secondary">Spare Part
Management</a>

<a href="add_product.php" class="list-group-item">Add Spare Parts</a>

<a href="product_list.php" class="list-group-item">List Spare Parts</a>

<a class="list-group-item"> Total Products: <span class="badge badge-
secondary">

```

```

        <?php

            //Display total product numbers

            $qi =mysql_i_query($con,"select * from table_product");

            echo mysql_i_num_rows($qi);

        ?>

    </span></a>

</div>

</div>

</div>

</div>

<br />

<div class="row">

    <div class="col-sm-6">

        <div class="list-group">

            <a class="list-group-item list-group-item-success">Staff Management</a>

            <a href="add_staff.php" class="list-group-item">Add Staff</a>

            <a href="list_staff.php" class="list-group-item">List Staffs</a>

            <a class="list-group-item"> Total Staffs: <span class="badge badge-success">

        <?php

            //Display total staff numbers

```


Codes in 'logout.php' page:

```
<?php

session_start();

//Check if a user click logout link

if(isset($_GET["logout"]) && ($_GET["logout"]=="true")){

    //Clear all session's information

    session_unset();

    session_destroy();

    //Redirect to login page

    header("location:login.php");

}

?>
```

Codes in 'connection.php' page:

```
<?php

//Database information

$con = mysqli_connect("localhost","ptc","RootAdmin11!!","PTCDB")

or die(mysqli_error($con));

}
```

?>

Codes in 'header.php' page:

```
<nav class="navbar navbar-expand-sm bg-light">

  <div class="container-fluid">

    <ul class="navbar-nav">

      <li class="nav-item">

        <a class="nav-link" href="index.php">

          Dashboard, Hello <?php echo $_SESSION["adminName"].", ";?>

          <?php echo ($_SESSION["role"]==1)?"You are Admin":"You are Staff";?>

        </a>

      </li>

    </ul>

  </div>

</nav>
```

Codes in 'left_menu.php' page:

```
<div class="col-md-3">

  <!--Start Invoice Management-->

  <div class="list-group">
```

```
<a class="list-group-item active">Invoice Management</a>

<a href="create_invoice.php" class="list-group-item">Create Invoice</a>

<a href="list_invoice.php" class="list-group-item">List Invoices</a>

<a href="list_history.php" class="list-group-item">List Histories</a>

</div>

<!--End Invoice Management-->

<!--Start Spare Part Management-->

<div class="list-group">

  <a class="list-group-item active">Spare Part Management</a>

  <a href="list_car_brand.php" class="list-group-item">List Car Brands</a>

  <a href="product_list.php" class="list-group-item">List Spare Parts</a>

</div>

<!--End Spare Part Management-->

<!--Start Staff Management-->

<div class="list-group">

  <a class="list-group-item active">Staff Management</a>

  <?php

  /*If role is admin, so shows these 2 menu items to use.

  But if role is not admin, so hides these 2 menu items.

  */
```

```

        if($_SESSION["role"] == "1"){

?>

<a href="list_staff.php" class="list-group-item">List Staffs</a>

<a href="salary.php" class="list-group-item">Salary</a>

<?php

    }

?>

<a href="attendance.php" class="list-group-item">Attendance</a>

<a href="list_utility.php" class="list-group-item">List Utility</a>

</div>

<!--End Staff Management-->

<!-- Start Income/Expense -->

<div class="list-group">

    <a class="list-group-item active">Income/Expese</a>

    <?php

        /*If role is admin, so shows these 4 menu items to use.

        But if role is not admin, so hides these 4 menu items.

        */

        if($_SESSION["role"] == "1"){

?>

```

```
<a href="summary.php" class="list-group-item">Net Income</a>

<a href="list_invoice.php" class="list-group-item">All Incomes</a>

<a href="salary_detail.php" class="list-group-item">All Salary Expenses</a>

<a href="all_asset.php" class="list-group-item">All Assets</a>

<?php

    }

?>

<a href="list_utility.php" class="list-group-item">All Utility Expenses</a>

<a href="service_income.php" class="list-group-item">Service Income</a>

</div>

<!-- End Income/Expense -->

<!-- Start Setting -->

<div class="list-group">

    <a class="list-group-item active">Setting</a>

    <a href="change_password.php" class="list-group-item">Change Password</a>

    <a href="logout.php?logout=true" class="list-group-item">Logout</a>

</div>

<!-- End Setting -->

</div>
```

Conclusion

Programming languages and software development is one of the most important parts in information technology or data science field. Its theory and syntax can be applied in technological fields to develop websites or web application especially it is used other fields include business, education, government or sport. Even though new technology grows rapidly, programming languages and software development is playing as an important role and still used along to it.

Some useful scripting and languages such as HTML, CSS, JavaScript, jQuery, Bootstrap are the one of the best to build front-end and PHP is for back-end with MySQL database connection for data storing.

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ITDS620 - Assignment Rubric

Student's Full Name: Mony Ho

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Category	Marks Allocation	Marks Attained	Comments
1. System Architecture	40 marks	31	
2. Functionality	40 marks	34	
3. Code Quality	20 marks	15	
*** Penalty *** This penalty is for papers that do not meet the assignment requirements. (i.e. word count, format, etc.)	(-5)		
Total marks allocated and achieved:	100 marks	80	